

Enslaved Domestic Work in an Atlantic Sephardic Household

Natália da Silva Perez

Department of History, Erasmus University Rotterdam

dasilvaperez@eshcc.eur.nl

Abstract

Sephardic Jews were involved in the burgeoning Atlantic trade of the seventeenth century, which linked Europe, Africa, and the Americas. As a highly mobile community, they may have lived in various places throughout their lives. As the Sephardic community settled in Amsterdam in the early-to-mid seventeenth century, they had to contend with issues that these travels brought to the fore, one of which was the boundary between enslavement and paid employment. While living in the Americas, Sephardic merchants often had enslaved people working in their households. What happened, though, when they brought these people to Amsterdam? By a close reading of the scant documentation available, this article shows the agency – and its limits – of two young women of African descent who were employed as enslaved domestic workers by a Sephardic merchant.

Keywords: Enslavement; Slavery; Amsterdam; Sephardic Jews; Atlantic; Amsterdam; Domestic service; households

Introduction¹

On 26 September 1656, merchant Eliau Burgos signed two contracts at the office of notary Benedict Baddel, in Amsterdam. The first of them consisted of an agreement between him and a 24-year-old woman designated as ‘Juliana de Burgos negra.’ In this contract, Juliana committed herself to board a ship to Barbados with Eliau Burgos ‘para o servir em tudo e por tudo’

1 This research was funded by the Danish National Research Foundation (DNRF 138).

(‘to serve him in everything and for everything’). The second contract was made between Eliau Burgos and a young woman who was fourteen years old, referred to as ‘Esperança de Burgos negra,’ and presented a similar commitment on Esperança’s part: she would board the ship to Barbados in Eliau Burgos’ company to serve him. The Burgos family had left the Dutch colony of Pernambuco in northeastern Brazil for Amsterdam when the colony reverted to the control of the Portuguese crown in 1654.² The Sephardic Jewish community that existed in that colony under the Dutch government had to leave once the Portuguese repossessed northern Brazil, and as I have discussed elsewhere, the Burgos household’s migration to Amsterdam is part of this wider colonial context. Importantly for the present discussion, the available evidence indicates that at least Juliana had come as a slave to Amsterdam with Eliau Burgos’ household when they left Pernambuco.³

In this article, I will present a commented close reading of the two contracts, made two years after the Burgos’ arrival in Amsterdam, between Eliau Burgos, on the one hand, and each of the two women, on the other. I show how linguistic, graphic, and spatial clues in these two documents help to tease out traces about how domestic work was organized in the Burgos household, a family of the Atlantic Sephardic diaspora.⁴ This analysis, which is inspired by a micro-historical approach, provides clues to understand domestic work in a Sephardic Jewish household in the context of the Atlantic sugar trade.

Running a Sephardic Jewish Household in the Diaspora

According to Tirtsah Levie Bernfeld, it was common for members of the Sephardic Jewish community in Amsterdam and elsewhere to employ domestic servants from among people who did not belong to their ethno-religious community.⁵ Eliau Burgos’ employment of Juliana and Esperança as domestic servants seems to fit this pattern, since both were women of African origin or descent purchased to work as slaves. In this context, a

2 da Silva Perez, “Privacy in Recife, Freedom in Amsterdam”; Wiznitzer, *Jews in Colonial Brazil*; Vainfas, *Jerusalém Colonial: Judeus Portugueses no Brasil Holandês*; Bodian, “Hebrews of the Portuguese Nation.”

3 Stadsarchief Amsterdam (SAA), Notarieel Archief 5075, inv. no. 2271, Not. Adriaen Lock, digital pages 766, 767, 768, 1 November 1656.

4 Schreuder, *Amsterdam’s Sephardic Merchants and the Atlantic Sugar Trade in the Seventeenth Century*.

5 Levie Bernfeld, “Masters Maids and Mistresses: Aspects of Domestic Life among the Portuguese Jews in the Seventeenth-Century Dutch Republic,” 27.

question raised by Levie Bernfeld becomes relevant: how skilled in normative Judaism were these domestic workers? Did the Burgos household fit within the parameters discussed by Levie Bernfeld, that is, was it one of those households where ‘Portuguese mistresses, mostly brought up in a Catholic environment, had only a vague notion as to how to run a kosher household and were little informed about all the *minhagim* around the Sabbath and the various Jewish holidays?’

At present, no information can be ascertained from the extant documents about the Burgos family’s level of familiarity with rules of normative Judaism. All I can conclude from the evidence available is that Eliau Burgos was married, but nothing is known about how much his wife might have known about the religious rules:

Eliu de Burgos disse e declarou que [illegible] por Ele sua mulher nem outro qualquer seu Parente Amigo ou Aliado...
(‘Eliu de Burgos said and declared [illegible] by him his wife nor any other whosoever his relative friend or ally...’)

Although we cannot deduct from these contracts whether or not Eliau Burgos’ wife was well-versed in the knowledge necessary to run a normatively Jewish household, we do have circumstantial evidence that Eliau Burgos’ family had a certain level of commitment to the Jewish communities where they lived. The first indication of this comes from Arnold Wiznitzer, who includes the name ‘Elyau Burgos’ in his ‘List of Members of the Jewish Community in Dutch Brazil as Transcribed from the Minute Book of Congregations Zur Israel and Magen Abraham (1648-54).’⁶ A second indication of the Burgos family as members of their Jewish community comes from the multiple mentions of the name Eliau Burgos from 1654 to 1656 in the income and expense books of the Sephardic community in Amsterdam. More specifically, Eliau Burgos is listed as being expected to contribute ‘promessas’ on 2 Tishrei 5415, on 4 Nisan 5415, on 3 Tishrei 5416, and on 4 Nisan 5416.⁷ The term ‘promessas’ refers to voluntary contributions towards charity. The other common contributions of ‘finta’ and ‘imposta’ were considered mandatory for *yehedim* (‘permanent congregation members, plural’) and

6 Wiznitzer, *Jews in Colonial Brazil*, 137.

7 SAA 334, inv. no. 174, p. 65, “2 Tishrei 5415” f 3:2; *ibid.*, p. 94, “4 de Nisan 5415”, f 3:6; *ibid.*, p. 123, “3 Tishrei 5416” f 0: 12; *ibid.*, p. 150, “4 Nisan 5416, f 0: 12.”; however, he did not pay these *promessas* as can be deducted from what is being mentioned there on p. 178, 14 Tishri 5417: f 8:2. This sum of f 8: 2 he still owed the Amsterdam Portuguese community. Also interesting is that he paid progressively less.

the absence of these contributions in the case of Eliau Burgos suggests that he was not considered a permanent member of that community.⁸ Indeed, as the contracts with Juliana and Esperança show, Eliau Burgos intended to relocate his household permanently to Barbados, where he could potentially join the community as a *yehid* ('permanent congregation member, singular'). These pieces of evidence only indicate that the Burgos household was part of the Jewish community, but do not reveal whether the family actually followed the religious rules.

Why did Eliau Burgos want to guarantee in writing that the two women come with his family to Barbados? We know from another document that Burgos declared having purchased Juliana to be his slave when she was about ten or eleven years old.⁹ Esperança was fourteen years of age when she signed the contract with Burgos two years after arriving in Amsterdam. Since both women had worked for the Burgos family from an early age, they might have been exposed to the religious rules observed in a Jewish household. But Burgos might also have simply needed maids to help with tasks outside the kitchen, caring for children or doing other work around the house that did not require in-depth knowledge of religious rules. In other words, there is no extant evidence about Juliana's and Esperança's level of knowledge of normative Judaism or kashrut rules.

Juliana's and Esperança's contracts are silent on any details about specialized tasks that would have to be performed in a Jewish household. Both their contracts, however, have something to say about the proficiency or skills with which the women were expected to perform their tasks. For example, in Esperança's contract we can read the following:

... para o servir em tudo e por todo sedu e tarde o [illegible] de dito anos bem fielmente, com mto primor e respeito em tudo no que pelo dito sr. Eliau de Burgos lhe for mandado...
(‘...to serve him in everything and for everything early and late [illegible] of said years very loyally, with much perfection and respect in all which said mister Eliau de Burgos order her...’)

8 According to Wiznitzer, ‘finta’ referred to a ‘special tax apportioned among members, according to their means, to make up deficiencies in the revenue of the Congregation.’ ‘Imposta’ referred to ‘tax on commercial transactions. Income tax paid by members of the Congregation.’ Finally, ‘promessas’ referred to ‘vows for charitable funds, corresponding to the Hebrew Nedarim.’ Wiznitzer, “The Minute Book of Congregations Zur Israel of Recife and Magen Abraham of Mauricia, Brazil,” 295–98. See Swetschinski, *Reluctant Cosmopolitans*.

9 SAA, Notarieel Archief 5075, inv. no. 2271, Not. Adriaen Lock, Digital Folios 765v. , 1 November 1656,

In Juliana's contract we can read a very similar passage, with the difference that in her case we have some clues about the word that is illegible in Esperança's contract (see above). In Juliana's contract, the passage contains a stricken through word, and reads as follows:

... para o servir em tudo e por tudo cedo e tarde o ~~espaço~~ [stricken through] [superscript: 'discurso'] de tres anos bem fielmente com mto primor e respeito em tudo no que pelo dito Eliau de Burgos lhe for mandado...

(‘...to serve him in everything and for everything early and late the ~~space~~ [stricken through] [‘course’] of three years very loyally, with much perfection and respect in all which the said mister Eliau de Burgos orders her...’)

Comparing these two excerpts, it becomes evident that the contracts made explicit that the women were expected to perform their tasks well (‘com mto primor’) and that they were also expected to have deference towards their enslaver (‘respeito em tudo no que pelo dito Eliau de Burgos lhe for mandado’) though we do not learn anything about what their tasks were. General or vague terms indicating that servants were expected to serve their masters with respect and loyalty were common. They are also present, for example, in last wills left by members of the Portuguese Nation in which the servants would receive gifts in recognition of such desirable behavior.

We also come across the first major difference between the contracts Eliau Burgos made with Juliana and with Esperança: Juliana's contract has a limited time frame, Esperança's does not. Juliana's contract stipulated a limited term of three years for her services, whereas Esperança's contract did not mention a specific number of years, simply indicating, ‘said years.’

Next in the text, the contract also specifies what commitment Eliau Burgos made with the women in return for their services. In the case of Esperança, the contract says the following:

... prometeu e promete por esta de a levar em sua comp.^a embarcada no dito navio livre de sua pessoa, frete e mais gastos e ademais disso de a [illegible, perhaps: “entreter”] de tudo o que lhe for necessário tanto de bibida e comida que vestir e calsar e o que mais lhe for necessario, comessando o dito termo de dito Annos do dia que for chegada nas ditas Barbadas em Diante e passados eles X...

(‘... promised and promises by this [document] to take her in his company on board the said ship of her own accord, free of freight charges and other expenses and, moreover, to provide her with everything necessary, be it

drink and food and what to dress and wear [on her feet] and whatever else is necessary, starting the said term of said years from the day of arrival in said Barbados onwards and once passed X...')

In the case of Juliana's contract, this section of the text is almost identical, except for the specified term of three years:

... prometeu e promete por esta de a levar em sua comp^a embarcada no dito navio livre [superscript: 'de sua pessoa'] de frete e mais gastos e ademais disso de a entreter de tudo o que lhe for necessario tanto de bibida e comida que vestir e calsar e o que mais lhe for necessario, comessando o dito termo de tres annos do dia que for chegada nas ditas Barbadas em diante X...

('... promised and promises to take her in his company aboard the said ship of her own accord, free of freight charges and other expenses and moreover to provide her with everything she needs, be it drink and food and what to dress and wear [on her feet] and whatever else is necessary, starting the said term of three years from the day of arrival in said Barbados onwards X...')

From this point on, the similarities between the contracts wane, and interpreting these two documents requires a higher level of attention. Notice that an X appears at the end of each excerpt above (section 1 in both figures 1 and 3). This X indicates that additional text, which appears in the left margin of each of the documents, must be inserted at the end of the excerpt (section 2 in both figures 1 and 3). The content of these marginal notes diverges strongly in each **contract**.

In Juliana's contract, the marginal text says the following:

X passados eles ficara a dita Juliana livre e desobrigada deste contrato para se ir donde bem lhe parecer ou de continuar se bem lhe estiver ('X after they have passed the said Juliana will be free and released from this contract to go wherever she sees fit or to continue if all is well')

In Esperança's contract, the marginal note says something quite different:

X e fazendo o dito sr Eliau de Burgos bem como a dita Esperança ficará toda sua vida em seu serviço ('X and doing it the said mr Eliau de Burgos as well as the said Esperança will remain all his/her life in his/her service')

The very first concern in interpreting these passages is to which person do ‘sua vida’ and ‘seu serviço’ refer. In other words, how should this passage from Esperança’s contract be translated from the Portuguese? Would only Esperança remain *her* life in *his* service? Or should we instead interpret the excerpt to imply some level of reciprocity, where both Eliau Burgos and Esperança would remain ‘their lives’ at ‘each other’s service’? The pronouns ‘sua’ and ‘seu’ in Portuguese give us cause to pause because they are gendered in a different way than the equivalent pronouns in English: ‘sua’ appears in the feminine because ‘vida’ is a feminine noun, and ‘seu’ in the masculine because ‘serviço’ is masculine. Here, *vida* and *serviço* could potentially mean either Esperança’s *vida* and *serviço*, or it could also mean both Esperança’s and Eliau Burgos’ *vida* and *serviço*.

But there are more complications in interpreting Esperança’s contract. After the X that refers to the marginal text described above, there is an important passage that appears stricken through. The stricken text in Esperança’s contract is almost the same as what appears in the marginal note in Juliana’s contract (compare section 1 of figure 3 and section 2 of figure 1), and says:

X ficará a dita Esperança livre e desobrigada deste [illegible, perhaps: ‘contrato’] para se ir donde bem lhe parecer ou de continuar se bem lhe estiver
 X and the said Esperança will be free and released from this [illegible, perhaps ‘contract’] to go wherever she sees fit or to continue if all is well

Why were the lines that stated that Esperança would become free stricken through, and replaced by lines that stated that she would serve Burgos forever? What caused Eliau Burgos to make such a contract with Esperança, given that, if Esperança was already Eliau Burgos’ slave, her status already implied service for life? In order to answer these questions, I had to puzzle over some aspects of the spatial organization of the documents.

Inferring Meaning from the Spatial Organization of the Contracts

A first aspect of spatial organization that I notice is that Juliana’s and Esperança’s contracts are written on the same sheet of paper, back-to-back. On the recto side, written as the first of the two, is Juliana’s contract, and Esperança’s comes on the verso side, the second to be drafted. Thanks to the digital interface of the Amsterdam City Archives, historians like me can use

the digital surrogates of the originals while still maintaining much of the spatial and material information that comes from consulting the original. And in fact, the digital surrogates of these documents provided by the Amsterdam City Archives allow for some types of manipulation—notably zooming in and out—that can give opportunities for additional inferences.¹⁰

Observing Juliana's contract, the reader might quickly notice that there were a few false starts in the drafting of the text. A total of five text sections can be perceived on the page (see figure 1). Let me describe them here in reading order. The section marked with number 1 consists of the main text. Section number 2 consists of the text represented by the X, that should be inserted in place of the X in the main body of text. Section number 3 is represented by a # sign and lists the names of witnesses 'dos sres Aaron Navairo e David Israel e mais.' This list of witnesses should be inserted in the place where a # appears in the main text, two lines from the bottom of section 1. Finally, we have section number 5, where a substantial addition was made to the contract, requiring a new signature by Eliau Burgos. The text of section 5 says the following:

[illegible] dia mes e Anno a tras escrito parecendo diante mim notario e testigos e dito sr Eliau de Burgos disse e declarou que [illegible] por Ele sua mulher nem outro qual quer seu Parente Amigo ou Aliado no discurso dos ditos tres annos atras declarados não poderão venderse dita negra Juliana nem mesmo acabados Eles, senão ficará livre para ir onde bem lhe estiver ou de continuar se bem lhe estiver. Feito como acima Elyau Burgos [illegible] day month and year written before appearing before me notary and witnesses and said mr Eliau de Burgos said and declared that [illegible] by him his wife nor any other relative, friend or ally in the course of the said three years declared before will not be able to sell said Black Juliana not even once they are finished, otherwise she will be free to go wherever she likes or to continue if all is well. Done as above Elyau Burgos

Why were these extra passages added to the contract outside of the main text area in section 1? Perhaps they indicate that Eliau Burgos was dictating to the notary and changing his mind, adding details that he intended to include in the contract but that he might have missed on the first go. Perhaps it was the notary formulating on the fly the ideas in contractual terms, as he heard the declarations of his client. Or perhaps it was Juliana who might have interfered on her own behalf, reacting to what she heard Eliau Burgos

¹⁰ Lit, *Among Digitized Manuscripts*, 51.

say as he dictated the contract, requesting for details about her rights to freedom to be specified more clearly in the text. (She did not know how to read, but from Eliau Burgos' description of her, she seems to have been a person with initiative.)¹¹

If we take a step back from the text of Juliana's contract and try to imagine the moment of the drafting, a picture starts to emerge where we have Eliau Burgos, Juliana, and four witnesses—Manuel Lavelho, Daniel Israel, Aron Navarro and Salomon de la Broÿes—all present before a notary public, about to sign a document that stipulated Eliau Burgos' and Juliana's mutual rights and obligations to each other. As I have discussed elsewhere,¹² the relationship between the parties of the contract was marked by a drastic imbalance of power. On the one hand, we have Eliau Burgos as the enslaver, and on the other we have Juliana as the enslaved. The only reason that allowed for a contract to be made between them in the first place was the fact that they were no longer in a colony but rather in Amsterdam, a city where slavery was purportedly disallowed. Indeed, the city of Amsterdam had a provision for the enslaved person to reclaim their freedom:

vermogen deselve personen haere voorsz Meesters ende Vrouwen voor den Gerechte deser Stede te doen dagen ende hen al daer rechtelyck vry te doen verklaren¹³

('may such persons summon their masters and mistresses before the Justice Department of the City to declare them legally free there')

As previous research has shown, Juliana must have understood—from being in contact with the members of the Afro-Atlantic community in the city of Amsterdam—that she had the right to be free.¹⁴ The contract with Eliau Burgos suggests that she was endeavoring to act on this right, negotiating conditions with her owner for her to become free: after three years of service, she would obtain her freedom.

But the contract also indicates that Eliau Burgos might not have had the intention to free Juliana in the terms that she might have expected, following the city's ban on slavery. I come to this conclusion because he includes in the contract the condition that Juliana's three years of service would only

¹¹ da Silva Perez, "Privacy in Recife, Freedom in Amsterdam."

¹² da Silva Perez, "Privacy in Recife, Freedom in Amsterdam."

¹³ Rooseboom, *Recueil van verscheyde keuren, en coustumen*, 186.

¹⁴ Ponte, "Al de swarten die hier ter stede comen' Een Afro-Atlantische gemeenschap in zeventiende-eeuws Amsterdam"; Hondius, "Black Africans in Seventeenth-Century Amsterdam"; da Silva Perez, "Privacy in Recife, Freedom in Amsterdam."

start once they arrived in Barbados. Eliau Burgos, faced with the reality that his right to hold slaves was not guaranteed in Amsterdam, tried to arrange a contract in which he could safeguard against the possibility of actually having to let Juliana go free. He did so by imposing the condition that Juliana must go to Barbados in order to get her benefits from the contract. The fact that the Portuguese word for slave is not mentioned anywhere in either of the contracts indicates that Eliau Burgos was trying to follow the letter of the law, while at the same time trying to evade the substance of the law. But for Juliana, there was no guarantee that this contract, which gave her freedom, would be regarded as valid in Barbados, where she would easily be considered as a slave.

In this context, let us go back to Juliana's contract, more specifically to the additional text that appears on the top left margin shown on figure 1, section 5. This textual addition is one more indication that Juliana might have been actively requesting for details to be included in the contract, as she pondered the conditions imposed on her freedom. The text on section 5 is admittedly difficult to read. First, it was added on the narrow space of the margin, leading to unclear handwriting. Second, the ink used by the notary bled, making several words difficult to parse. Despite these caveats, it seems that the text safeguards against the possibility of Juliana being sold before the period of three years was completed:

Ele sua mulher nem outro qual quer seu Parente Amigo ou Aliado no [illegible, perhaps: 'curso'] dos ditos tres annos atras declarados não poderão venderse dita negra Juliana...

(him his wife nor any other relative, friend or ally in the course of the said three years declared before will not be able to sell said negra Juliana')

Paleographic readings can constantly be reinterpreted. Other eyes might look at the words and question whether my reading of the word 'vender' is correct or not (see figure 2, detail of Juliana's contract). Could it be that Juliana might have been advocating for herself, asking her enslaver not to sell her before she could obtain her freedom under the conditions he was imposing, asking him to include this in her contract? This question, unfortunately, cannot be definitively answered.

When read in the context of Juliana's contract, Esperança's contract looks slightly less complicated. Three text sections can be discerned, as shown in figure 3. Section number 1 contains the main text of the contract, including the stricken-through passage saying that Esperança would be granted freedom. Section number 2 is positioned on the left margin and

Figure 2: Detail of Juliana’s contract showing the phrase interpreted as ‘não poderão vender.’

contains the text that replaces the stricken through passage, referred to as X, saying that Esperança (and Eliau Burgos) would remain ‘toda sua vida em seu serviço.’ Finally, section number 3 contains the signatures of the parties to the contract and witnesses.

Suppose we engage in a similar exercise for Esperança’s contract of imagining the situation at the moment of this document’s making. In that case, we can picture Esperança and Eliau Burgos together with four witnesses. In this case one of the witnesses differs from those who signed Juliana’s contract—the names are Manuel Lavelho, Daniel Israel, Aron Navarro, and Hector [unclear, perhaps: ‘Frigoma’]. Could Juliana have been present, too? It seems unlikely.

There is no evidence that Esperança requested Eliau Burgos to be freed, as he reported that Juliana did.¹⁵ Esperança was younger, making it possible to believe that she might not have discovered that slavery was banned in Amsterdam. Perhaps Juliana told Esperança about it and insisted that Eliau Burgos make a contract for both women. If we imagine that the women were friends, this scenario seems possible. But in case the women were not friends, there could be a different explanation why Eliau Burgos made a contract for Esperança that did not grant her freedom.

The addition of the text in section 5 of Juliana’s contract was undoubtedly made before Esperança’s contract was written. In other words, Juliana’s contract must have been completed, as we read it today, before the notary moved on to draft Esperança’s contract. The reason for this assertion is that each line of section number 1 in Esperança’s contract stops before the blots formed on the right side of the page, which came from the ink bleeding from

¹⁵ SAA, Notarieel Archief 5075, inv. no. 2271, Not. Adriaen Lock, Digital Folios 765v-766, 1 November 1656.

Figure 3: Esperança's contract, Stadsarchief Amsterdam: Inventory 5075, Notary 44 Benedict Baddel, Minuutacten Folder 980, Digital Folio 77.

section 5 of Juliana's contract. One question remains: why was the passage granting Esperança freedom removed from her contract?

Could it be that it was Eliau Burgos who asked the notary to replace the passage granting freedom for the marginal note in section 2, stating she would remain in his service for life? Why did the marginal note use the formulation 'Eliu Burgos bem como a dita Esperança,' implying a mutual arrangement of service for life?

I already commented on the fact that Esperança was significantly younger than Juliana. I also inferred that Esperança must have come into the Burgos household at an early age. If we imagine that the Burgos were the only family that Esperança had ever known, indeed, we can imagine that she wanted to follow them to Barbados. Could it be that Esperança welcomed Eliau Burgos' patriarchal protection, even if it meant remaining in an enslaved state? Did Esperança fully apprehend what her legal status as enslaved meant in the bigger picture? Again, these are not answerable questions with the evidence presently at hand, but nonetheless it is important to ask them.

Conclusion

When Eliau Burgos and his family moved from the colony in Pernambuco to Amsterdam, at least one enslaved woman, Juliana, had come with them, while it remains unclear if a second enslaved woman, called Esperança, was purchased in Pernambuco, Amsterdam, or elsewhere. Both women seem to have been enslaved in the Burgos household from childhood. In employing women who did not come from their own ethno-religious group, the Burgos household showed characteristics shared with other households of the Sephardic diaspora. When they decided to relocate to Barbados, these two women were expected to follow them and continue to work as their enslaved domestic workers.

Eliu Burgos signed contracts with each woman to guarantee that they would follow him and his family to Barbados, but the terms of the contracts were not the same in each woman's case. Juliana's contract would grant her freedom after three years of service but imposed a condition that the three years would only start after they arrived in Barbados. Esperança's contract, on the other hand, maintained the status quo, stipulating that 'Eliu de Burgos bem como a dita Esperança ficará toda sua vida em seu serviço,' a formulation that in Portuguese implies reciprocity but remains ambiguous regarding the real advantages for Esperança.

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About the author

Natália da Silva Perez is Assistant Professor of Popular Culture in Historical Perspective at ~~the~~ Erasmus University Rotterdam. Her research focuses on comparatively examining the lives of women of low and high social standing in the early modern period. She works with comparative, transnational, and intersectional methodologies to study women's interactions with their families, communities, authorities, and society in general. For that, she combines microhistorical with trans-imperial approaches to the early modern period, often aided by computational and data-driven approaches to textual analysis.